

SeaMark M36 update

Version 2

Description

The purpose of the DMP is to give an overview of the data produced or collected during the SeaMark project with plans to make them available publicly. The goal is to list the data, to know which one can be made public, which one have to be confidential, and to upload the public ones to an open repository in order to make them publicly available. The DMP will make sure that third parties can access the research data and that the data will be collected, identified, stored, registered, and preserved.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Seaweed based market
applications
(corda_____he::101060379)

Researchers

Organizations

Fermentation Expert AS, Lunds Universitet, Sjøkøvin, Aarhus Universitet, ALGAplus, Ruitenberg Ingredients B.V., Aventure AB, Vattenfall Vindkraft AS, Aalborg Universitet, Submariner network for blue growth ewiv, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Ocean Forest, Algolesko, Danmarks Tekniske Universitet, Stichting Wageningen Research, Carlsberg AS, National University of Ireland Galway, UAB Sirputis, Universiteit Utrecht, Københavns Universitet, SPF Ocean Rainforest, Algaia, Matis OHF, Nofima, The Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture Research

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [SeaMark M36 update](#)

Description:

The purpose of the DMP is to give an overview of the data produced or collected during the SeaMark project with plans to make them available publicly. The goal is to list the data, to know which one can be made public, which one have to be confidential, and to upload the public ones to an open repository in order to make them publicly available. The DMP will make sure that third parties can access the research data and that the data will be collected, identified, stored, registered, and preserved.

Researchers:

Organizations:

[Fermentation Expert AS](#)

[Lunds Universitet](#)

[Sjokovin](#)

[Aarhus Universitet](#)

[ALGAplus](#)

[Ruitenbergh Ingredients B.V.](#)

[Aventure AB](#)

[Vattenfall Vindkraft AS](#)

[Aalborg Universitet](#)

[Submariner network for blue growth ewiv](#)

[Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique](#)

[Ocean Forest](#)

[Algolesko](#)

[Danmarks Tekniske Universitet](#)

[Stichting Wageningen Research](#)

[Carlsberg AS](#)

[National University of Ireland Galway](#)

[UAB Sirputis](#)

[Universiteit Utrecht](#)

[Kobenhavns Universitet](#)

[SPF Ocean Rainforest](#)

[Algaia](#)

Matis OHF

Nofima, The Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture Research

Contact: Sør Dahl Patrick Berg (patrick.sordahl@nofima.no)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Seaweed based market applications \(corda____he::101060379\)](#)

Project: [Seaweed based market applications](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

[Descriptions](#)

[Ulva phenotyping](#)

[Ulva phenotyping data generated by SeaMark](#)

[Produced by WP1, University of Galway](#)

[Linked to SeaMark deliverables: D1.1, D1.3, D1.5](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel 2.x Worksheet (xls)
- Plain Text File

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To identify high-production Ulva strains

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

SeaMark project

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Ulva breeders, Ulva researchers, policy makers, industry.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Ulva phenotyping

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the repository

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE project

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2026-06-30

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

By the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

ronan sulpice (orcid: [0000-0002-6113-9570](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6113-9570))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Fucoidans coextraction dataset.

The dataset will gather analytical results from the various biomass (pretreated biomass, raw biomass, co-product, etc.), extraction process data (time, pH, temperature, etc.), product characterization and observational data (comments).

Data will be specific according to product targeted (especially regarding analytical parts). The data collected will aim to link the extract composition to a process and by extend with other WP, a concept of feasibility (technical and economical). The data will be, most of the time, divided in two parts:

- Process data (seaweed quantities, power used, time, temperature...)
- Analytical data (Extract and by-product compositions, yields, mass balance...)

Produced by WP5, ALGAIA

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D5.2, D5.3, D5.6, D7.4, D8.1, D8.3 D8.6, D9.7

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

Sample or specimen data, observational data, and experimental data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

The data collected will be used for selection and protocol optimization purposes, benchmarking and technico-economic assessment.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data is generated by ALGAIA and results remain the property of ALGAIA

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- Industry

ALGAIA and companies developing fucoidans applications, academic partners, stakeholder in the ingredient and bioactive industry, policy makers.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Fucoidans coextraction dataset.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially confidential

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with ALGAIA

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Jeremy Brebion, ALGAIA

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Results on biomass are exclusive

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Commercial scale sales for commercial products from Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

Commercial scale sales and deliveries

Produced by WP7, Nofima

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D7.6

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

400 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To get feedback from commercial scale sales and deliveries

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Interviews, survey

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

To the consortium

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Commercial scale sales for commercial products from Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Morten Heide (orcid: [0000-0002-7590-1415](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7590-1415))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data belongs to companies

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Monitorization of abiotic factors

Collected and historical data on the abiotic factors that strongly influences the seaweed production (yield and quality)

Produced by WP2, ALGAplus

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D2.6

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

Sample and specimen data and observational data

1.1.5 What is its format?

SIARD (Software-Independent Archiving of Relational Databases)

Didn't find the option of choosing "none" or "other" but the format will be linked to a software that will be developed during the project

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

Control of everyday conditions that influences the seaweed growth and understanding on the effect of these conditions on seaweed production.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ALGApplus

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

ALGApplus; coastal lagoon users (for data relative to the lagoon water entrance); other potential aqua farmers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Monitorization of abiotic factors

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The data belong to the companies and are commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with ALGAplus

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Margarida Martins

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

The health-promoting effect of fermented seaweed

The dataset consists of a number of variables (biomarkers) derived from different biological material (blood, saliva, milk, faeces, intestinal tissue) from sows fed with commercial sow feed and sows fed with commercial sow feed supplemented with EP199 (fermented seaweed). The biomarkers used are inflammation markers, markers for oxidative stress, etc. that can describe the health status of the sows in various ways. Further, the dataset contains clinical markers (body temperature, respiratory rate, appetite, etc.). The faecal samples generate DNA to describe the microbiome at different times in the first 2 parities of the sows. The intestinal samples are only taken from a subset of the sows and used for metabolomic and transcriptomic analyses.

Produced by WP4, Aalborg University, Copenhagen University, FEXP

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

1.1.5 What is its format?

Comma Separated Values

and Fastq format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

TB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

The complete dataset will make it possible to determine the modulatory effects of EP199 on gut function and the general immune status of the sows at different stages of the first 2 parities.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data are collected from sows housed in a commercial sow farm

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

Researchers who study topics related to the microbiome (in pigs as well as humans, as pigs are often a model for humans), sow health, pig health and welfare as well as seaweed. Manufacturers of seaweed and feed with supplementation of seaweed.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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b. ENA (European Nucleotide Archive)

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) is an open, supported platform for the management, sharing, integration, archiving and dissemination of sequence data.

Database of record and platform for data management: ENA comprises both the globally comprehensive data resource that preserves the world's public-domain output of sequence data (Read more about ENA Content here) and a rich portfolio of tools and services to support the management of sequence data.

A data foundation: as nucleotide sequencing becomes increasingly central to applied areas such as healthcare and environmental sciences, ENA has become a foundation upon which scientific understanding of biological systems may be assembled. Our users comprise data submitters, data coordinators for sequence-based studies, direct data consumers and secondary service providers (e.g., UniProt, RNACentral, EBI Metagenomics, Ensembl, Ensembl Genomes, ArrayExpress) that build on ENA services and content.

Data coordination: our data coordination partnerships span the life sciences, covering such areas as livestock genomics, marine biotechnology, biodiversity, pathogen surveillance and stem cell biology. Within these partnerships, we support data operations variously through the provision of technology,

standards, data analysis, training, support and web/API data portals. Read more here.

Ambition: we are committed to the utility of the ENA platform and to achieving the broadest reach and utility of sequencing technology and data.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

The health-promoting effect of fermented seaweed

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Various bioinformatic tools

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through repositories

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Leslie Foldager (orcid: [0000-0002-2639-826X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2639-826X))

Dataset responsible

b. Marianne Kaiser (orcid: [0000-0002-9962-5582](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9962-5582))

Dataset responsible

c. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Nilay Gökgöz (UCPH)

Pia Sørensen (FEXP)

Andrew Richard Williams (UCPH)

Dennis Sandris Nielsen (UCPH)

Dataset participants

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Biorefinery plant implementation plan

A detailed report on the programme for consent, licensing, design, building modifications, equipment purchasing, installation and commissioning of the biorefinery. The programme will include detailed project plan, resource allocation and risk management plan. The report also will include suitable locations identified, buildings and needed equipment for the desired operation as well as describe personal (Results of T3.1)

Produced by WP3, Oceanium

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D3.2

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

TBC

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

To determine the associated costs, risks and issues we need to address for the transition into commercialization of the business.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

Any bio-refining company wanting to commercialize their business

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Biorefinery plant implementation plan

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially confidential

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Mike Roberts, Oceanium

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Recommendations for scenario testing for commercial products from Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

Recommendations from the feasibility studies as basis for testing scenarios

Produced by WP7, Nofima

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D7.4

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

400 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To create recommendations for testing scenarios

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Interviews, survey, secondary data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

To the consortium

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Recommendations for scenario testing for commercial products from Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Morten Heide (orcid: [0000-0002-7590-1415](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7590-1415))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data belongs to companies

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Ulva strain collection

List of the Ulva strains being used in SeaMark, including strains collected during the Genialg project and newly-collected strains.

Produced by WP1, University of Galway

Linked to SeaMark deliverable: D1.3

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New data and re-using existing data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

300kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

These strains will be used for identification of elite Ulva strains for aquaculture.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

SeaMark and Genialg project

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Ulva breeders, Ulva researchers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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Unless specified otherwise, Zenodo metadata may be freely reused under the CC0 waiver.

These Terms of Use are subject to change by CERN at any time and without notice, other than through posting the updated Terms of Use on the Zenodo website.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Ulva strain collection

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the repository

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE project

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2026-06-30

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

By the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

ronan sulpice (orcid: [0000-0002-6113-9570](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6113-9570))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Alginates coextraction dataset.

The dataset will gather analytical results from the various biomass (pretreated biomass, raw biomass, co-product, etc.), extraction process data (time, pH, temperature, etc.), product characterization and observational data (comments).

Data will be specific according to product targeted (especially regarding analytical parts). The data collected will aim to link the extract composition to a process and by extend with other WP, a concept of feasibility (technical and economical). The data will be, most of the time, divided in two parts:

-Process data (seaweed quantities, power used, time, temperature...)

-Analytical data (Extract and by-product compositions, yields, mass balance...)

Produced by WP5, ALGAIA

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D5.2, D5.3, D5.6, D7.4, D8.1, D8.6, D9.7

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

Sample or specimen data, observational data, and experimental data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

The data collected will be used for selection and protocol optimization purposes, benchmarking and technico-economic assessment.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data is generated by ALGAIA and results remain the property of ALGAIA

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

ALGAIA, companies using alginates as ingredients

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Alginates coextraction dataset.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially confidential

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with ALGAIA

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Jeremy Brebion, ALGAIA

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Results on biomass are exclusive

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

In vitro simulated gastrointestinal digestion of feed supplement prototypes developed by AAU

UCPH: Will perform in vitro simulated gastrointestinal digestion of the developed feed supplement prototypes. The following types of data will be generated: Amount of NaOH used (as a proxy for fermentation activity), acetate, propionate and butyrate formation, gut microbiome composition.

Produced by WP4, UCPH

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Comma Separated Values

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

UCPH: To assess the activity of the developed prototypes in the pig gut

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

UCPH intern

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Other Seamark partners + external stakeholders investigating the effect of seaweed and seaweed derived products on gastrointestinal health

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

ERDA

<https://www.erda.dk/>

ERDA or Electronic Research Data Archive at University of Copenhagen (KU/UCPH) is meant for storing, sharing, analyzing and archiving research data. The intended audience is employees, their collaboration partners and students. ERDA delivers safe central storage space for own and shared files,

interactive analysis tools in addition to archiving for safe-keeping and publishing. You can use ERDA as a secure network drive from anywhere and it also comes with a stand-alone file synchronization service similar to Dropbox, but with the data safely stored locally at UCPH.

ERDA is delivered by SCIENCE HPC Center and is formally for the faculty of Science, but others have access mainly for data archiving and publication with UCPH DOIs. A roll-out to all of UCPH is underway to support the general UCPH Data Management Guidelines.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

In vitro simulated gastrointestinal digestion of feed supplement prototypes developed by AAU

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the repository

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Dennis S. Nielsen and Nilay Gökgöz (UCPH)

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Biorefinery processing of 450 T ww *S. latissima*

Report on the successful processing of 450 tonnes (wet weight) *S. latissima* to fucoidan, beta-glucan, fibre and kelp residue for packaging and each products detailed description related to processing method, product description, and the potential markets and applications (Results of T3.2).

Produced by WP3, Oceanium

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D3.3

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

TBC

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record

To have a summary of product yields of different batches

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Processing data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry

The company, project partners, regulators, customers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Biorefinery processing of 450 T ww S. latissima

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially confidential

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Charlie Bavington, Oceanium

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Ulvan modifying enzymes and enzymatic processing of Ulvan

Characterization of enzymes active on ulvan, substrate specificity, substrate and products from enzymatic modification, structural components, properties (e.g. bioactivity, molecular mass, composition etc).

Produced by WP6, Matis, LUN, UTR

Linked to SeaMark deliverables: D6.4, D6.5, D6.7

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format
- Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

300kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

For designing and evaluating enzymatic processes for production of ulvan and ulvan oligosaccharide derivatives with bioactive properties, product prototypes

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the Partners:

MATIS (Iceland), University of Lund (Sweden), University of Utrecht (Netherlands)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- The public
- Industry

Emerging seaweed bio-refineries and downstream associated end-user companies, scientific community and public.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GenBank

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>

GenBank® is a comprehensive database that contains publicly available nucleotide sequences for almost 260 000 formally described species. These sequences are obtained primarily through submissions from individual laboratories and batch submissions from large-scale sequencing projects, including whole-genome shotgun (WGS) and environmental sampling projects. Most submissions are made using the web-based BankIt or standalone Sequin programs, and GenBank staff assigns accession numbers upon data receipt. Daily data exchange with the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and the DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ) ensures worldwide coverage. GenBank is accessible through the NCBI Entrez retrieval system, which integrates data from the major DNA and protein sequence databases along with taxonomy, genome, mapping, protein structure and domain information, and the biomedical journal literature via PubMed. BLAST provides sequence similarity searches of GenBank and other sequence databases. Complete bimonthly releases and daily updates of the GenBank database are available by FTP

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Ulvan modifying enzymes and enzymatic processing of Ulvan

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The data will be evaluated by the partners, some may need to be temporary protection of IP , for intended publication and of value for further research of the partners.

Depends on the data possible utilization possibilities and interest of partners and companies within the consortium. It also depends on legislation/regulations within EU and specific countries regarding compatible with the Nagoya protocol concerning access and benefit sharing (ABS)

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through repositories

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Gudmundur Hreggvidson (Matis)

Eva Nordberg Karlsson (LUN)

Justyna Dobruchowska (UTR)

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Needs to be compatible for access and benefit (ABS), sharing according to EU and specific countries of Genetic resources

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Fish production data to include in software for farm management

Data on feeding rates, dissolved oxygen, weight at harvest, water DIN (dissolved inorganic nitrogen)

Produced by WP2, ALGAplus

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

Filtered water from the fish ponds is the main input to our seaweed production; we need to know it in order to monitor/predict growth in seaweed as well as food safety protocols.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ALGApus

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

For ALGApus only; depending on the outcome of the software development, for other land-based/on-shore IMTA farms.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Fish production data to include in software for farm management

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The data belong to the companies and are commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with ALGApplus

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Margarida Martins

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Co-coextraction of Ulva products.

The dataset will gather analytical results from the various biomass (pretreated biomass, raw biomass, co-product, etc.), extraction process data (time, pH, temperature, etc.), product characterization and observational data (comments).

Data will be specific according to product targeted (especially regarding analytical parts). The data collected will aim to link the extract composition to a process and by extend with other WP, a concept of feasibility (technical and economical). The data will be, most of the time, divided in two parts:

Process data (seaweed quantities, power used, time, temperature...)

Analytical data (Extract and by-product compositions, yields, mass balance...)

Produced by WP5, ALGAIA

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D5.4, D5.5, D6.7, D7.4, D8.1, D8.6, D9.7

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

Sample or specimen data, observational data, and experimental data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

The data collected will be used for selection and protocol optimization purposes, benchmarking and technico-economic assessment.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data is generated by ALGAIA and results remain the property of ALGAIA

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

Algaplus, ALGAIA, Commercial companies working with Ulva sp.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Co-coextraction of Ulva products.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially confidential

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with ALGAIA

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Jeremy Brebion, ALGAIA

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Results on biomass are exclusive

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Mechanised seeding of *Saccharina latissima*

Large scale seaweed farming is in demand for a high capacity and efficient seeding process. Direct seeding techniques are the most likely choice as it has been used already for some years and the best perspective to automate for large scale application. However, the technology is still in an early phase of development (TRL 6-7) and requires improvement on the concept, the adhesives and the equipment to seed and deploy.

A major step forward has been the application of the 2-step direct seeding concept. A small, hand operated prototype apparatus will come available and will be used as starting point for further development. This apparatus will seed on land and the seeded ropes will be transported to the site. The large offshore application however will demand seeding and deployment instantly on site. The seeding machine has to be combined with a system to attach the rope to the cultivation rig. Cultivation rigs at ORF are based on vertically positioned ropes; at ALO and OF horizontally positioned ropes are used. The seeding and deployment equipment should be able to serve both systems.

The work will be conducted in lab systems, tanks and also directly at sea. The basic interest is the adherence capacity of the tested glues and improvements of adherence by the specific pre-treatments of the rope. Beside this we will study the durability of the adherence capacity.

The developed seeding machine will contribute to this result. The machine is mostly tested on its capacity of distributing the seed nicely over the substrate. Secondly to apply the glue/pre-treatment to the rope. The machine is also evaluated for its practical application and the economy.

Control is the standard hand massaged seeding.

Produced by WP2, Ocean Rainforest

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D2.1 and D2.4

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- To improve a product

Evidence for the intended functioning and improved economy; scaling of the seeding process

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ORF own measurements

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Economy
- Industry

To the seaweed farmers; the developer of the seeding machine; to the commercial sales of the machines

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Mechanised seeding of *Saccharina latissima*

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially sensitive, the glue and machine will be subject to IPR

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Ocean Rainforest

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Job Schipper, Ocean Rainforest

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Patent application

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Saccharina latissima crosses

List of the *S. latissima* crosses carried out in SeaMark.

Produced by WP1, CNRS.

Linked to SeaMark deliverable: D1.2

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

400kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To keep on record

To keep a record of the crossing experiments for WP1

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

SeaMark project

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Kelp breeders, kelp researchers.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Saccharina latissima crosses

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the repository

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE project

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2026-06-30

Under embargo until the end of SeaMark to allow publication

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

By the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

J. Mark Cock (orcid: [0000-0002-2650-0383](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2650-0383))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Ensure sustainable use of any data obtained

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Monitoring of selected *Saccharina latissima* strains in Faroe Islands and Brittany

ORF (Faroe Islands at Funningsfjørður & Gøtuvík) and ALO (Britany, France) will provide rig space for testing at least three isolated *Saccharina latissima* strains of local ecotypes from WP1, T1.2. The monitoring of growth will be done by ORF and ALO and shared with WP1 partners for feedback.

Produced by WP2, Ocean Rainforest, Algolesko, Station Biologique Roscoff

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D1.4 and D1.6

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Portable Network Graphics

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1000kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To improve a product

To increase yield of cultivated *Saccharina latissima* from the North of Europe to the South.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ORF and ALO and SBR are together collecting the data.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Economy
- Industry

The seaweed producers, investors

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Monitoring of selected Saccharina latissima strains in Faroe Islands and Britany

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Ocean Rainforest, Algolesko or SBR

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Urd Bak (orcid: [0000-0002-9679-6933](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9679-6933))

Dataset responsible (ORF)

b. J. Mark Cock (orcid: [0000-0002-2650-0383](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2650-0383))

Dataset responsible (SBR)

c. Mathilde Lemoine (orcid: [0000-0001-5985-8042](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5985-8042))

Dataset responsible (Algolesko)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Enzymatic processing of laminarin

Characterization of enzymes active in laminarin, substrate specificity, Substrate and products from enzymatic modification: structural components, properties (e.g. bioactivity, molecular mass, composition etc).

Produced by WP6, Matis, LUN, UTR

Linked to SeaMark deliverables: D6.3, D6.4, D6.5

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format
- Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

300kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

For designing and evaluating enzymatic processes for production of valuable polysaccharide derivatives with bioactive properties, product prototypes

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the Partners:

MATIS (Iceland), DTU (Denmark) University of Lund (Sweden) University of Utrecht (Netherlands)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- The public
- Industry

Emerging seaweed bio-refineries and downstream associated end-user companies, scientific community and public.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GenBank

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>

GenBank® is a comprehensive database that contains publicly available nucleotide sequences for almost 260 000 formally described species. These sequences are obtained primarily through submissions from individual laboratories and batch submissions from large-scale sequencing projects, including whole-genome shotgun (WGS) and environmental sampling projects. Most submissions are made using the web-based BankIt or standalone Sequin programs, and GenBank staff assigns accession numbers upon data receipt. Daily data exchange with the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and the DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ) ensures worldwide coverage. GenBank is accessible through the NCBI Entrez retrieval system, which integrates data from the major DNA and protein sequence databases along with taxonomy, genome, mapping, protein structure and domain information, and the biomedical journal literature via PubMed. BLAST provides sequence similarity searches of GenBank and other sequence databases. Complete bimonthly releases and daily updates of the GenBank database are available by FTP.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Enzymatic processing of laminarin

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The data will be evaluated by the partners, some may need to be temporary protection of IP , for intended publication and of value for further research of the partners.

Depends on the data possible utilization possibilities and interest of partners and companies within the consortium. It also depends on legislation/regulations within EU and specific countries regarding compatible with the Nagoya protocol concerning access and benefit sharing (ABS)

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through repositories

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee

- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Gudmundur Hreggvidson (Matis)

Eva Nordberg Karlsson (LUN)

Justyna Dobruchowska (UTR)

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Needs to be compatible for access and benefit (ABS), sharing according to EU and specific countries of Genetic resources

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Ratio of biomass losses from harvest to storage

Detailed description of biomass losses from harvest to storage

Produced by WP2, ALGAplus

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational and experimental data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

Economic analysis and improvement of critical stages of biomass transitions between processes.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ALGApplus

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

ALGApplus operational and management team; Specific partners in consortia.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Ratio of biomass losses from harvest to storage

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The data belong to the companies and are commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with ALGAplus

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Margarida Martins

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Enzymatic processing of fucoidans

Characterization of enzymes active on fucoidans, substrate specificity, substrate and products from enzymatic modification: structural components, properties (e.g. bioactivity, molecular mass, composition etc).

Produced by WP6, Matis, DTU, UTR

Linked to SeaMark deliverables: D6.4, D6.5, D6.6

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format
- Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

300kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

For designing and evaluating enzymatic processes for production of valuable polysaccharide derivatives with bioactive properties, product prototypes

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the Partners:

MATIS (Iceland), DTU (Denmark) University of Lund (Sweden) University of Utrecht (Netherlands)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- The public
- Industry

Emerging seaweed bio-refineries and downstream associated end-user companies, scientific community and public.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GenBank

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>

GenBank® is a comprehensive database that contains publicly available nucleotide sequences for almost 260 000 formally described species. These sequences are obtained primarily through submissions from individual laboratories and batch submissions from large-scale sequencing projects, including whole-genome shotgun (WGS) and environmental sampling projects. Most submissions are made using the web-based BankIt or standalone Sequin programs, and GenBank staff assigns accession numbers upon data receipt. Daily data exchange with the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and the DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ) ensures worldwide coverage. GenBank is accessible through the NCBI Entrez retrieval system, which integrates data from the major DNA and protein sequence databases along with taxonomy, genome, mapping, protein structure and domain information, and the biomedical journal literature via PubMed. BLAST provides sequence similarity searches of GenBank and other sequence databases. Complete bimonthly releases and daily updates of the GenBank database are available by FTP.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Enzymatic processing of fucoidans

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The data will be evaluated by the partners, some may need to be temporary protection of IP , for intended publication and of value for further research of the partners.

Depends on the data possible utilization possibilities and interest of partners and companies within the consortium. It also depends on legislation/regulations within EU and specific countries regarding compatible with the Nagoya protocol concerning access and benefit sharing (ABS)

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through repositories

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee

- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Gudmundur Hreggvidson (Matis)

Maria Delgaard Mikkelsen (DTU)

Justyna Dobruchowska (UTR)

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Needs to be compatible for access and benefit (ABS), sharing according to EU and specific countries of Genetic resources

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Development plan for product specification

Report on the production specifications for product safety, composition, packaging and storage.

Produced by WP3, Oceanium

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D3.1

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

TBC

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

The report will provide a detailed overview of the chemical composition of the envisioned products and describe safety as well as the packaging details and storage type and shelf life (Results of T3.1).

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data will be extracted from extended trial runs and associated analysis together with packaging and transit trials to determine the most suitable materials and methods

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry

The company, project partners, regulators, customers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Development plan for product specification

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially confidential

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Mike Roberts, Oceanium

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

LCA data set

Data of energy, inputs and outputs of seaweed cultivation

Data of energy, inputs and outputs of seaweed fibre production

Data of energy, inputs and outputs of pig feed supplement production

Produced by WP9, Wageningen Research (WUR)

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D9.7

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Sample or specimen data, observational data, derived or compiled data, other data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To assess the environmental impact of 3 seaweed-based products (with help of Life Cycle Assessment)

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Ocean Rainforest, Oceanium, Fermentation Experts

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

LCA practitioners

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

LCA data set

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The data set cannot be shared as it contains sensitive data from the consortium partners.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Sander van den Burg (orcid: [0000-0003-3849-482X](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3849-482X))

Dataset responsible

b. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Jeroen Westrate

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Contains sensitive data provided by the consortium partners, shared under NDA.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Product analysis data

A comprehensive report describing the analysis of all products to provide certificates of analysis including microbiology, heavy metal, iodine, and allergen to fully describe the food safety of the new products and any potential risk related to the application of these products (Results of T3.3).

Produced by WP3, Oceanium

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D3.4

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

TBC

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

Produce a product analysis summary

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

In house and external analysis

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry

The company, project partners, regulators, customers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Product analysis data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially confidential

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Charlie Bavington, Oceanium

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Post-harvest processing into storage stable products

Upscaling of post-harvest processes in the Faroe Islands by ORF and in Portugal by ALGP to clean, fragment, and produce storage stable and transportable intermediate seaweed raw material according to specifications of WP3-5 at a speed of 10T ww/h for *S.latissima* and 2T ww/day for *Ulva* sp. Upscaling of ensilage into 20ft containers for *S. latissima* by ORF and small scale ensilage test for *Ulva* sp. by ALGP will also be performed.

Produced by WP2, Ocean rainforest and ALGApplus

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D2.3

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational and experimental data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1000kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To improve a product

To improve post-harvest processing for scale-up

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ORF is collecting the data for the processes in the Faroe Islands, ALGP is collecting the data for processes in Spain.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- The public
- Industry

The seaweed producers and the users of the produced products.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Post-harvest processing into storage stable products

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Ocean Rainforest

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Urd Bak (orcid: [0000-0002-9679-6933](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9679-6933))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Ratio of biomass losses from harvest to storage

Detailed description of biomass losses from harvest to storage

Produced by WP2, ALGAplus

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational and experimental data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

Economic analysis and improvement of critical stages of biomass transitions between processes.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ALGAplus

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

ALGAplus operational and management team; Specific partners in consortia.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Ratio of biomass losses from harvest to storage

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The data belong to the companies and are commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with ALGApplus

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Margarida Martins

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Mutant Sequence data

Sequence data from a specific gene of interest showing wild type sequence in a control sample and the wild type sequence including a desired nucleotide change in the isolated genetic variant.

Produced by WP1, Traitomic, Carlsberg laboratory

Linked to SeaMark deliverable: D1.7

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

Generating new data and re-using existing data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

Experimental and sample or specimen data

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format
- Plain Text File

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

Improve seed material through advanced genetic screening and selective breeding. The data will also set the foundation for the use of genomic selection for seaweed breeding of *Ulva* sp. and *S. latissima* to increase cultivation yields.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Sequencing data from isolated genetic variants

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Algal Genetics Group, Integrative Biology of Marine Models Department UMR 8227 CNRS-UPMC, Roscoff, France and Ocean Forest in Faroe Islands.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Mutant Sequence data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the repository

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE project

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

By the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Toni Wendt (orcid: [0000-0002-8149-7682](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8149-7682))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Fucoidan product dossier

A report detailing safety, origin and composition of the fucoidan product to enable regulatory approval (Results of T3.4).

Produced by WP3, Oceanium

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D3.5

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

new and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

TBC

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions

Enable regulatory approval

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data from peer-reviewed literature, and from product analysis (T3.4)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry

The company, regulators, customers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

DOI

The dataset is confidential

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Confidential

The dataset won't be openly available

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Fucoidan product dossier

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Company interest

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

it won't

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

NA

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

it gives the name of the company, that can then be contacted if wanted

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Charlie Bavington, Oceanium

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Growth and site parameters in a new site in FO

Based on existing rig designs, an open ocean seaweed cultivation rig (up to 40,000 seeded meters) will be tested by ORF in one new site in the Faroe Islands seeded with *S. latissima* and evaluated for techno-economic performance.

Produced by WP2, Ocean rainforest

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D2.2

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational and experimental data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1000kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

To investigate the performance of a new open ocean seaweed cultivation unit, giving insight in scale-up potential.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ORF is collecting the data for the site in the Faroe Islands.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Economy
- Industry

Seaweed producers & investors

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Growth and site parameters in a new site in FO and NO

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Ocean Rainforest

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Urd Bak (orcid: [0000-0002-9679-6933](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9679-6933))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Chemical and biological characteristics post fermentation

The dataset consists of experimental data obtained from several series of fermentations. The data involves a large number of seaweed fermentation samples performed with different parameters. Each fermentation sample is accompanied with data related to chemical and biological composition and function.

Produced by WP4, Aalborg University

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D4.1 and D4.3

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

500kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

Experimental data is collected to characterize chemical and biological composition of a series of fermentations. It is believed that additional information can be extracted by coupling biological information with comprehensive chemical analysis of the fermentation samples.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The experimental data is collected using various spectroscopic and spectrometric methods.

It will be defined for each column how the data is collected.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

The data will immediately be useful for WP4 partners.

Later, the data may be useful for stakeholders involved in commercializing food and feed products that contain various types of seaweed.

Research institutions involved in research related to the biorefining of seaweed may find the data accompanying the publications particularly useful.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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These Terms of Use are subject to change by CERN at any time and without notice, other than through posting the updated Terms of Use on the Zenodo website.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Chemical and biological characteristics post fermentation

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2024-06-30

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Christian Olesen (orcid: [0000-0003-3647-8834](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3647-8834))

Dataset responsible

b. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Reinhard Wimmer (Aalborg University)

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Pilot scale sales for commercial products from Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

Pilot scale sales and deliveries

Produced by WP7, Nofima

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D7.5

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

400 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To get feedback from pilot scale sales and deliveries

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Interviews, survey

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

To the consortium

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Pilot scale sales for commercial products from Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Morten Heide (orcid: [0000-0002-7590-1415](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7590-1415))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data belongs to companies

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Saccharina latissima strain collection

List of the *S. latissima* strains being used in SeaMark, including strains collected during the Genialg project and newly-collected strains.

Produced by WP1, CNRS.

Linked to SeaMark deliverable: D1.2, referred to in D1.4 and D1.6.

Multi-sheet Excel file with information about the initial sporophyte/gametophyte sampling and the isolation and use of the clonal gametophyte strains.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

300kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To develop a product
- To improve a product

These are the strains that will be used for crosses in WP1.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

SeaMark and Genialg projects

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Kelp breeders, kelp researchers.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Saccharina latissima crosses

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the repository

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE project

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2026-06-30

Under embargo until the end of SeaMark to allow publication

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

By the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

J. Mark Cock (orcid: [0000-0002-2650-0383](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2650-0383))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Ensure sustainable use of any data obtained

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Flagship products and go-to-market strategy for Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

Specification of flagship products and preliminary go-to-market strategy

Produced by WP7, Nofima

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D7.1

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

Interviews

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

400 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

To have an overview of flagship products and allow further development of go-to-market strategies

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Interviews of Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

To the consortium

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Flagship products and go-to-market strategy

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Morten Heide (orcid: [0000-0002-7590-1415](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7590-1415))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data belongs to companies

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Beta-glucan product dossier

A report detailing safety, origin and composition of the fucoidan product to enable regulatory approval (Results of T3.5).

Produced by WP3, Oceanium

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D3.6

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

TBC

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions

Enable regulatory approval

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data from peer-reviewed literature, and from product analysis (T3.5)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry

The company, project partners, regulators, customers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

DOI

Dataset won't be openly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Data won't be available

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

data won't be available

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Beta-glucan product dossier

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Company interest

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

it won't

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Charlie Bavington, Oceanium

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Mechanized harvesting at sea for kelp growing on vertical grow lines.

Mechanised harvesting technologies at sea for *S. latissima* will be developed and demonstrated by Ocean Rainforest (ORF) at their cultivation site in the Faroe Islands with a capacity aiming at 1500 m/hr of vertical grow lines on a MACR. The mechanised harvesting technologies will be based on currently available concepts and prototypes. We will compare new harvesting data with previous harvest data using manual harvesting.

Produced by WP2, Ocean rainforest

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D2.4

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

40kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

To better understand the cost reduction obtained by mechanized harvesting.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Observations and measurements at sea by Ocean Rainforest

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Economy
- Industry

Primary producers of kelp on vertical line systems, investors

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Mechanized harvesting at sea for kelp growing on vertical grow lines.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercial IP interest for Ocean Rainforest, a patent could be relevant for ORF

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Ocean Rainforest

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Urd Bak (orcid: [0000-0002-9679-6933](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9679-6933))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Seaweed chemical characterization

Chemical characterization of the produced biomass.

Produced by WP2, ALGAplus

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D2.6

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

Sample or specimen data and derived or compiled data

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To keep on record
- To improve a product

To monitor and ensure biomass quality.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ALGApplus and external certified Lab.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

ALGApplus & partners using/testing the biomass produced.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Seaweed chemical characterization

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The data belong to the companies and are commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with ALGApplus

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Margarida Martins

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Data for socio-economic impacts SeaMark product

Data from supply chain characterization, value chain analysis and techno-economic assessment together with literature and national statistics will be utilized to determine potential impacts from upscaling macroalgae production in terms of employment, revenue and GVA

Produced by WP8, Sjukovin, Blue Resource

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D8.4

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational data, derived or compiled data, reference or canonical data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

To assess socio-economic impacts of upscaling macroalgae production- To support the business exploitation plans in T8.5

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Value chain analysis, techno-economic analysis, national statistics

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Macroalgae researchers of economic and social sciences

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

The data will be partly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Only parts of the data will be open, the economic data is sensitive and will be kept as that. Can be shared under conditions described in the grant agreement.

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Data for socio-economic impacts SeaMark product

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

Partly open

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The economic data is sensitive for companies

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Be being uploaded to Zenodo

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2027-06-30

12 months after project end, for time to publish

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Magni Laksafoss (orcid: [0000-0002-7526-9376](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7526-9376))

Dataset responsible

b. Unn Laksá (orcid: [0000-0002-5782-4858](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5782-4858))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Saccharina latissima phenotyping

S. latissima phenotyping data generated by SeaMark.

Dataset from WP1, CNRS

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D1.2, D1.4, D1.6

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

400kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To identify high-production *S. latissima* strains

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

SeaMark

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

Kelp breeders, kelp researchers.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Saccharina latissima phenotyping

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the repository

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2026-06-30

Under embargo until the end of SeaMark to allow publication

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

By the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

J. Mark Cock (orcid: [0000-0002-2650-0383](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2650-0383))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Ensure sustainable use of any data obtained

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Data for characterization of supply chains of SeaMark product

Interviews and other communications with producers, processors and other actors containing qualitative and quantitative information needed to characterize and illustrate de supply chain and actors involved within the supply chains for all 12 SeaMark products (deliverable D8.1).

Produced by WP8, Sjokovin

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D8.1

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To get information for supply chain characterization and background data to perform VCA

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Interviews to producers, processors, and other actors in the supply chain

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Macroalgae researchers in economic aspects

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

The data will be partly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Only parts of the data will be open, the economic data is sensitive and will be kept as that. Can be shared under conditions described in the grant agreement

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Data for characterization of supply chains of SeaMark product

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

Partly open

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Industrial property

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Be being uploaded to Zenodo

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2027-06-30

12 months after project end, for time to publish

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Unn Laksá (orcid: [0000-0002-5782-4858](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5782-4858))

Dataset responsible

b. Magni Laksafoss (orcid: [0000-0002-7526-9376](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7526-9376))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Industrial property

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Data for techno-economic analysis of flagship products

Notes from the literature, interviews with producers and other communication containing qualitative and quantitative information needed to perform techno-economic analysis of the SeaMark flagship products (deliverables D8.3 and D8.6).

Produced by WP8, Nofima

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D8.3, D8.6

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational data, simulation data, derived or compiled data, reference or canonical data

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To get information needed to perform techno-economic analysis

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data come from literature and interviews

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

To researchers studying economic feasibility of processing macroalgae

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

The data will be partly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Only parts of the data will be open, data contain sensitive company information (production process details and prices).

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Data for techno-economic analysis of flagship products

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

Partly open

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Data contain sensitive company information (production process details and prices)

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Be being uploaded to Zenodo

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2027-06-30

12 months after project end, for time to publish

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Eirik Mikkelsen (Nofima)

Dataset responsible

b. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Katrine Eriksen (Nofima)

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data contain sensitive company information (production process details and prices)

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Seaweed farming equipment drawings and calculation

Engineering of seaweed farming equipment

Produced by WP2, Sirputis.

Linked to SeaMark deliverables: D2.2, D2.3, D2.4

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format
- AutoCAD Drawing

- Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To develop a product

To develop equipment which would meet needs of the project's applicant and partners

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

UAB, Sirputis

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

For equipment producers, further developers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Not decided yet on the repository

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Seaweed farming equipment drawings and calculation

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

No restrictions, but need to get UAB "Sirputis" permission to use it.

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Data will belong to Sirputis, who wish to keep a control over the re-use.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

By asking access to Sirputis

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Contact to Sirputis

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE project

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

The dataset won't be available openly on repositories.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

The data will be available upon request

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

By the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Milica Zygyte

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Quality control of seaweed biomass

Quality control info acquired throughout cultivation and biomass processing

Produced by WP2, ALGAplus

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To keep on record
- To combine with other data

To ensure biomass quality and traceability info for all produced batches.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ALGApus

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

ALGApus & partners using/testing the biomass produced.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Quality control of seaweed biomass

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The data belong to the companies and are commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with ALGAplus

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Margarida Martins

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Data for characterization of supply chains of SeaMark product - business exploitation

Information relevant for business exploitations plans, will be gathered from existing datasets generated for:

Value chain analysis – Task 8.2

Techno-economic analysis – Task 8.3

Socio-economic impacts – Task 8.4

Go-to-market strategies – WP7

Scenarios for inclusion of monetized ES in for business exploitation plans - T9.3 WP9

Produced by WP8, Sjokovin, Blue Resource

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D8.7

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

500kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

To produce business exploitation plans for upscaling macroalgae cultivation

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Datasets and interviews from previous tasks within WP7, 8 and 9

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

Industrial partners and entrepreneurs interested in macroalgae cultivation and biotransformation

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Data for characterization of supply chains of SeaMark product - business exploitation

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2025-06-30

12 months after project end, for time to publish

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage

- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Magni Laksafoss (orcid: [0000-0002-7526-9376](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7526-9376))

Dataset responsible

b. Unn Laksá (orcid: [0000-0002-5782-4858](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5782-4858))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Market application potential for commercial products from Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

Initial assessment of market application potential

Produced by WP7, Nofima

Linked to SeaMark deliverable D7.3

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

400 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To assess of market application potential

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Interviews, survey, secondary data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

To the consortium

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The data won't be publicly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The data won't be publicly available

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Market application potential for commercial products from Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Commercially sensitive

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Possibility to take contact with Oceanium, Fermentation Experts and Algaia

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Not Open)

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Morten Heide (orcid: [0000-0002-7590-1415](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7590-1415))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data belongs to companies

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Ecosystem service data set

For the quantification and valuation of the ES we need to collect data on them. This could be data on carbon capture, nutrient capture (clearance rate of nitrate and phosphor), biodiversity increase or abundance. In the period M1-M18 an operational, workable method to collect the relevant data in-situ was development of. In M18-28 the data was collected and analyzed in M25-30.

Produced by WP9, Wageningen Research & University (WUR) and Sjukovin

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D9.2, D9.3, D9.4, D9.5

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

28,7-283kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

We need this data to make quantitative analysis from this. We need to give monetized values to the ES, therefore we need to measure them precisely.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data collected at the cultivation sites.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

All tasks from WP9, to an extent WP8.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Ecosystem service data set

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2026-01-01

An embargo should possibly be applied until the end of the year 2025. We are aiming at submitting the data by September 2025 and hope to have it published by end of the year.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Sophie Koch (Sjokovin)

Dataset responsible

b. Sander van den Burg (orcid: [0000-0003-3849-482X](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3849-482X))

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Data for value chain analysis of flagship products

Notes from the literature, interviews with producers and other communication containing qualitative and quantitative information needed to perform value chain analysis of the SeaMark flagship products (deliverables D8.2 and D8.3).

Produced by WP8, WUR

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D8.2, D8.3

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational data, derived or compiled data, reference or canonical data

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To get information needed to perform VCA.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data come from literature and interviews

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

To researchers studying value chains macroalgae and to new companies.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

The data will be partly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

Only parts of the data will be open, the economic data is sensitive and will be kept as that. Can be shared under conditions described in the grant agreement.

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Data for value chain analysis of flagship products

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

Partly open

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Data contain sensitive company information (economic sensitive data on profits and investments)

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Be being uploaded to Zenodo

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2027-06-30

12 months after project end, for time to publish

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Sander van den Burg (orcid: [0000-0003-3849-482X](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3849-482X))

Dataset responsible

b. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Nera Herceglic (WUR)

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Data contain sensitive company information (economic sensitive data on profits and investments)

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Alginate lyases and data on products produced by enzyme catalysis

Characterization of alginate lyases, substrate specificity, Substrate and products from enzymatic modification: structural components, properties (e.g. bioactivity, molecular mass, composition etc).

Produced by WP6, Matis, DTU, LUN, UTR

Linked to SeaMark deliverables: D6.2, D6.4, D6.5

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Acrobat PDF 1.0 - Portable Document Format
- Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

300kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

For designing and evaluating enzymatic processes for production of valuable polysaccharide derivatives with bioactive properties, product prototypes

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the Partners:

MATIS (Iceland),

DTU (Denmark) University of Lund (Sweden) University of Utrecht (Netherlands)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- The public
- Industry

Emerging seaweed bio-refineries and downstream associated end-user companies, scientific community and public.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GenBank

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>

GenBank® is a comprehensive database that contains publicly available nucleotide sequences for almost 260 000 formally described species. These sequences are obtained primarily through submissions from individual laboratories and batch submissions from large-scale sequencing projects, including whole-genome shotgun (WGS) and environmental sampling projects. Most submissions are made using the web-based BankIt or standalone Sequin programs, and GenBank staff assigns accession numbers upon data receipt. Daily data exchange with the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and the DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ) ensures worldwide coverage. GenBank is accessible through the NCBI Entrez retrieval system, which integrates data from the major DNA and protein sequence databases along with taxonomy, genome, mapping, protein structure and domain information, and the biomedical journal literature via PubMed. BLAST provides sequence similarity searches of GenBank and other sequence databases. Complete bimonthly releases and daily updates of the GenBank database are available by FTP.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Alginate lyases and data on products produced by enzyme catalysis

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The data will be evaluated by the partners, some may need to be temporary protection of IP , for intended publication and of value for further research of the partners.

Depends on the data possible utilization possibilities and interest of partners and companies within the consortium. It also depends on legislation/regulations within EU and specific countries regarding compatible with the Nagoya protocol concerning access and benefit sharing (ABS)

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through repositories

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Url to the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Gudmundur Hreggvidson (Matis)

Anne S. Meyer and Maria Delgaard Mikkelsen (DTU)

Eva Nordberg Karlsson (LUN)

Justyna Dobruchowska (UTR)

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Needs to be compatible for access and benefit (ABS), sharing according to EU and specific countries of Genetic resources

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Seaweed production data

Details on production/cultivation data, namely on commercial strains versus selected strains.

Produced by WP2, ALGAplus

Linked to SeaMark deliverables D1.1 and D2.6

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

New and re-used data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

Sample or specimen data and observational data

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To keep on record
- To improve a product

Monitorization of seaweed growth.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ALGApplus

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Industry

ALGApplus

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

The data will be partly available

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

The data will only be partly uploaded to Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

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3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Seaweed production data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

Partly open

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The data belong to the companies and some are commercially sensitive

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Be being uploaded to Zenodo

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

By being described in the DMP which will be public on Zenodo

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE projects

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2026-06-30

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Covered by the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Margarida Martins

Dataset responsible

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Saccharina latissima ddRAD-seq genotyping

S. latissima ddRAD-seq genotype data generated by Genialg and SeaMark.

Produced by WP1, CNRS.

Linked to SeaMark deliverable

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

1.1.5 What is its format?

.fastq for the sequencing data (files listed in D1.2_Dataset_1_ddRAD.xlsx) and .vcf for the variant calling (D1.2_Dataset_2_variants.vcf).

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1166 files, each about 100 to 500 MB for the ddRAD-seq fastq files, 1.5 GB for the VCF file.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To identify high-production *S. latissima* strains

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Genialg and SeaMark

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

Kelp breeders, kelp researchers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The ddRAD-seq data is in EBI ENA where it is associated with specific accession numbers. The variant data will be deposited in Zenodo.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Saccharina latissima ddRAD-seq genotyping

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Under embargo until the end of SeaMark to allow publication.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the repository

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

URL of the data

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE project

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

2026-06-30

Under embargo until the end of SeaMark to allow publication

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

250

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

By the project

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

J. Mark Cock (orcid: [0000-0002-2650-0383](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2650-0383))

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Ensuring sustainable use of the data.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Raw Data Mastersheet SeaMark

Excel spreadsheet of raw data.

Produced by WP2, Nofima.

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

1.1.5 What is its format?

.xls

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

34kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

For growth trials at different sites in Norway

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Field data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Further comparative studies

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

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3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

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Yes

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Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Raw Data Mastersheet SeaMark

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the repository

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as relevant

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Yes

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3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

EC recommendation for H2020/HE project

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

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Set up of scientific and technical committee

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Other

By the project

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Philip James (0000-0003-0825-3435)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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